

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF ALOE FIBRE

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Aloe is very coarse or stiff in comparison with jute. In this investigation attempts have been made to find out the cause from a study of its chemical composition. It has been observed that the fibre contains a remarkably low lignin content and a high fat and α -cellulose contents contradicting the belief that the stiffness of lignocellulosic fibre is due to its high lignin, low fat and α -cellulose contents. From the study of the chemical composition of *Hibiscus cannabinus* fibres it appears that the stiffness of the Aloe fibre is due to its high xylan and polyuronides contents and not to its lignin, α -cellulose or fat contents.

The partition of India has resulted in a deficiency of jute for the Indian jute mills and as Aloe grows in India in considerable quantities in dry and rocky ground where growing of jute is unfavourable, this fibre appears to be a promising substitute for jute. Aloe has previously found an application in the manufacture of ropes and sacking. The fibres are, however, too harsh, stiff and coarse to be spun into medium weight yarns. To produce yarns for hessians, it is therefore necessary to find out means for softening the aloe fibres. The purpose of this paper is therefore to investigate the cause of stiffness of this fibre prior to devising means for improving its quality.

As the chemical composition of aloe fibre has not been determined previously the present investigation has been undertaken. It can be seen below that even the information available at present in the literature regarding the chemical composition of fibres of the same species e. g. sisal, is also incomplete and contradictory. α -Cellulose, lignin, hemicellulose, mineral matter, natural fats, nitrogenous and colouring matter are the usual constituents of the lignocellulose fibres. Hemicellulose is composed of hexosan of low molecular weight such as glucose, galactan and mannan, pentose like xylan and araban and polyuronides including pectin giving glucouronic and galactouronic acids. Mathew ("Textile Fibres", 1948, Chapman & Hall, p. 380) reports the composition of sisal fibre as moisture 11.5%, ash 1.0%, lignin 14.5% and cellulose 72%, but did not mention the values for total hemicellulose, α -cellulose, xylan, polyuronides, hexosans, fat and nitrogen contents of the fibre. Sarkar and co-workers (*J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1947, 63, 229) on the other hand, while investigating the acid nature of the vegetable fibres in relation to the basic dye absorption, reported the composition of sisal as lignin 6.27%, holocellulose 91.67%, α -cellulose 64.84%, ash 0.62%, carbon dioxide 1.16%, and furfural 12.20%. They, however, did not estimate the fat content of the fibre. There is thus a considerable difference between the composition of sisal fibres as reported by Mathew and that by Sarkar and co-workers. Aloe is likely to be different from sisal although both belong to the same species.

The stiffness of the lignocellulose fibres is said to be due to their high lignin content or the presence of hemicelluloses or both. From a study of the chemical composition of *Bimli* and *Mesta* fibres in this laboratory (Das, Mitra and Wareham, in the press) it appears that the stiffness of these fibres is not due to the presence of lignin but to the

hemicellulose, especially xylan and polyuronides. The present investigation was therefore undertaken to determine if the same is true for aloe fibre.

In this investigation colouring and nitrogenous matters have not been estimated as their percentages are negligible,

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample which was obtained from Madras was very coarse and stiff. In view of the fact that this fibre may vary in composition along the stem length, the sample was divided into 3 parts, root, middle and tip in such a way that these divisions were approximately equal in weight though not in length. For the purpose of comparison a sample of white jute (*C. Capsularis*) procured from 24-Parganas was also analysed which was not divided and therefore represented the whole plant stem. Four samples thus obtained were then air-conditioned.

Fat Content.—The fat content was determined by Soxhleting about 20 g. of the conditioned raw material with a mixture of alcohol and benzene (1 : 1 by volume) for 6 hours and after filtration, estimating the total solid content (dry wt.) of the extract. Moisture was determined on a counter sample and figures were calculated on the dry weight of the fibre. Substances other than fat, e. g. colouring matter etc. are also included in these figures but as their amounts are very small no corrections have been made. Experiments were carried out in duplicate. After extracting as above, the samples were dried in air, washed thoroughly in distilled water and dried in air again. Each sample was then cut into short lengths, bark and specks were removed as far as possible and then conditioned in air. These samples were then used for the subsequent experiments.

Ash Content.—Defatted conditioned fibre (2 g. approx.) was taken for each experiment for the estimation of ash content. The moisture of the fibre was determined on a counter sample and the results were calculated after making necessary corrections for the fat content.

Estimation of Lignin.—Both the modified 'sulphuric acid method' of Norman and Jenkin (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 2147) and the 'chlorite method' of Chattopadhyaya and Sarkar (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 12, 23) were used for the estimation of lignin, 2 g. of finely cut defatted fibre being used for each estimation.

For the 'sodium chlorite method' jute was treated with 0.7% sodium chlorite (textone) for 2 hours at the boil on a water-bath (liquor ratio 1 : 50) at p_H between 4.5 and 5 using acetic acid and sodium acetate buffer (Walpole). It was then filtered through a tared IG₃ sintered glass crucible and washed thoroughly with distilled water. The residue, as holocellulose, was then dried at 105° to a constant weight. The lignin was determined by the loss in weight and calculated on the dry weight of the original fibre.

α -Cellulose and Total Hemicelluloses.— α -Cellulose was estimated by treating the holocellulose obtained from the chlorite process as outlined above with sodium hydroxide solution according to the A. C. S. method modified by Sarkar and co-workers (*J. Text. Inst.*, 1948, 39, T44). The results were calculated on the dry weight of the raw fibre after necessary correction for its fat content. Hemicellulose contents were

calculated by deducting the sum of the corresponding values for α -cellulose, lignin, fat and wax and ash contents from 100. For this purpose the values obtained by chlorite process were used.

Estimation of Furfural.—Furfural was estimated by the method of Schorger (cf. Doree, "Method of Cellulose Chemistry", 1933, p. 361, Chapman & Hall, London) with slight modification of Chattopadhyaya and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*), the formula given by Doree (*loc. cit.*, p. 363) having been used for the calculation.

Estimation of Carbon Dioxide Value.—The method of Nanji, Paton and Ling (cf. Doree, *ibid.*, p. 372) was used in the determination of carbon dioxide, the period of boiling the fibre with hydrochloric acid being 3 hours. But as Sarkar, Majumder and Pal (*J. Text. Inst.*, 1948, 39, T44) showed that in the case of jute uronic acid carbon dioxide represented about 80% of the total carbon dioxide, small amount of carbon dioxide being obtained from α -cellulose (0.17%), glucose (0.4%), xylose (0.4%), the values of uronic acid carbon dioxide were calculated on the assumption that the same relationship also holds good for aloe fibres. The percentage polyuronides was then calculated from the relation given by Nanji, Paton and Ling (*loc. cit.*) as below.

$$\% \text{ Uronic CO}_2 \text{ calculated} \times 4 = \% \text{ uronic anhydride.}$$

It has been found by Norris and Resch (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1594) that the furfural due to polyuronides is 23.5% of the weight and that for α -cellulose due to Sarkar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) is 1.23%. The balance of the total furfural is derived from pentosan, the amount of pentosan as xylan being.

$$\frac{\text{Furfural} \times 100}{64.3} \text{ (Kröbers table)}$$

Hexosan Content.—Hexosan was calculated by subtracting the sum of pentosan and polyuronide from the total hemicellulose.

The results of the chemical analyses are shown in the table below where only the average values of the duplicate experiments are recorded.

TABLE I

	Aloe				White jute.
	Root.	Middle.	Tip.	Average.	
Fat content	2.17	2.01	2.44	2.21	0.82
Ash content	1.39	0.90	0.83	1.04	0.81
Lignin (H ₂ SO ₄ method)	6.74	5.30	6.46	6.17	11.78
Lignin (Chlorite method)	6.65	5.21	6.40	6.09	11.85
α -Cellulose	61.42	66.22	66.01	64.55	61.40
Total hemicellulose	28.37	25.66	24.32	26.12	25.12
Furfural	11.48	12.28	10.58	11.45	9.38
Carbon dioxide value	1.68	1.65	1.83	1.72	1.26
Polyuronides	5.38	5.28	5.84	5.50	4.04
Xylan	14.65	15.84	13.02	14.50	11.90
Hexosan	8.34	4.54	5.46	6.11	9.18

DISCUSSION

Aloe differs from jute by its remarkable low lignin content. It can be seen that this fibre, although contains a much higher proportion of fat and lower percentage of lignin, is very stiff, indicating that a higher fat and lower lignin content do not always result in soft fibres.

Chattopadhyaya and Sarkar's method (*loc. cit.*) of determining lignin for aloe fibres agrees well with the modified sulphuric acid method of Norman and Jenkin. Fat, ash, lignin and α -cellulose do not vary in any definite manner along the stem length of the aloe fibre but it appears that hemicellulose content is appreciably higher towards the root:

Aloe contains a higher percentage of α -cellulose than white jute contradicting the belief that soft fibres are those which contain less non-cellulosic matter.

Although the average hemicellulose content of aloe fibre is only slightly higher than jute, both xylan and polyuronides contents of the former are generally higher than the latter, in agreement with the view that lowest quality fibre contains the highest amount of xylan (cf. Powrie and Speakman, *J. Text. Inst.* 1943, 34, T77). The results therefore indicate that a higher xylan and polyuronide content and not lignin, fat or α -cellulose are responsible for the coarseness or stiffness of aloe fibre. This conclusion supports our previous view derived from the study on the chemical composition of *Hibiscus cannabinus* fibres (in the press).

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